

THE FIRST SURVEY INSTRUMENT

The following is an overview of the questions that were asked in the first survey.

DEMOGRAPHICS

- 1) Which of the following best describes your role at ING?
 - a. Software engineer
 - b. Tribe lead
 - c. Chapter lead
 - d. Product owner
 - e. IT manager
 - f. IT architect
 - g. Other
- 2) How many years of work experience do you have in the software development industry?
 - a. Less than 1 year
 - b. 1 to 5 years
 - c. 5 to 10 years
 - d. 10 to 20 years
 - e. More than 20 years
- 3) How long have you been working at ING?
 - a. Less than 1 year
 - b. 1 to 5 years
 - c. 5 to 10 years
 - d. 10 to 20 years
 - e. More than 20 years

FACTORS AFFECTING ON-TIME EPIC DELIVERY

- 4) In your experience, what factors (beyond the estimation process) affect the timeliness of your team's epic deliveries? (open-ended)
- 5) How do these factors influence the timeliness of epic deliveries?

THE SECOND SURVEY INSTRUMENT

The following is an overview of the questions that were asked in the second survey.

DEMOGRAPHICS

- 1) Which of the following best describes your role at ING?
 - a. Software engineer
 - b. Tribe lead
 - c. Chapter lead
 - d. Product owner
 - e. IT manager
 - f. IT architect
 - g. Other
- 2) How many years of work experience do you have in the software development industry?
 - a. Less than 1 year
 - b. 1 to 5 years
 - c. 5 to 10 years
 - d. 10 to 20 years
 - e. More than 20 years
- 3) How long have you been working at ING?
 - a. Less than 1 year
 - b. 1 to 5 years
 - c. 5 to 10 years
 - d. 10 to 20 years
 - e. More than 20 years

FACTORS AFFECTING ON-TIME EPIC DELIVERY

- 4) How much do each of the following factors impact the timeliness of your team's epic deliveries?

Included: Overview of 4-point Likert-scale questions for all 25 factors that were identified in the first survey. See Table 1 for an extract of the Likert-scale questions. The factors were presented in random order to the survey participants to reduce ordering bias. Short descriptions were included to explain the factors to participants.
- 5) Are there any factors or types of factors missing that affect the timeliness of your team's epic deliveries?

Factor	No impact	Small impact	Moderate impact	Large impact	Not applicable
Agile maturity The ability of a team to become more agile over time	()	()	()	()	()
Attentional focus Increased focus by reducing parallel work, and slicing backlog items in smaller and equal sizes	()	()	()	()	()
Bugs or incidents Impact of bugs and incidents in production	()	()	()	()	()
Collocation Impact of team members being geographically collocated (not distributed)	()	()	()	()	()
Communication Quality of communication with management and the customer	()	()	()	()	()
Executive support Active involvement of management and the commitment of required resources	()	()	()	()	()
Insufficient testing Lack of tests or poor quality	()	()	()	()	()
Lack of code quality Technical debt	()	()	()	()	()
Organizational alignment Impact of having a shared vision and strategy across the organization (priority alignment)	()	()	()	()	()
Organizational politics Bureaucracy and organizational politics	()	()	()	()	()
Organizational stability Impact of changes in management and organizational restructuring	()	()	()	()	()
Poor documentation Lack of source code documentation or poor source code documentation quality	()	()	()	()	()
Project criticality Whether the project involves business- or safety-critical systems	()	()	()	()	()
Project newness Whether new technology is being used or built to innovate	()	()	()	()	()
Project size Project scale; project duration, project effort, size of software systems and size of development teams	()	()	()	()	()
Refinement quality Quality of requirements analysis, and the process of refining an epic into a set of features and user stories	()	()	()	()	()
Regular delivery Impact of regularly delivering production ready software (short cadence)	()	()	()	()	()
Task dependencies Cross-team dependencies; caused by unaligned priorities and inconsistent schedules between dependent teams	()	()	()	()	()
Team capabilities Technical knowledge and skills of members of the development team	()	()	()	()	()
Team commitment The development team members' commitment to on-time delivery and their focus on achieving the team's purpose	()	()	()	()	()
Team maturity The impact of a development team being together for over a long period of time	()	()	()	()	()
Team stability Consistent composition of the development team	()	()	()	()	()
Technical dependencies Technical dependencies between software components (e.g., modules)	()	()	()	()	()
Unreliable infrastructure Unavailability or instability of infrastructure needed for software development and software testing (e.g., an unstable test environment)	()	()	()	()	()
User involvement Early and frequent interactions with the end user (represented by the product owner)	()	()	()	()	()

TABLE 1: Extract of the Likert-scale questions in the second survey. Here the factors are shown in alphabetical order. In the survey the factors were presented in random order to the participants.